

NDAC/LO/057
1985 May 24

The Cowling globals in Step 2/3, erratum (continued).
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In NDAC/LO/055 I defined a set of "compound" Cowling parameters c_i . By oversight, the corresponding differential coefficients were simply ⁱadded like the parameters, which made them in some cases much too large. The mean errors given in Table 1 should therefore be increased by factors $6(c_1)$, $3(c_2)$, $2(c_3)$ and $1.5(c_6)$. Also, a slightly different set of nine parameters has been found to be preferable. The conclusions in NDAC/LO/055 remain valid, however, except that the GR-deflection may not be measured to better than 0.5 % accuracy.